

Embedded Systems Profiling for an IoT Use Case

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Abstract—The following work was interested in developing an IoT application, and measuring its resource consumption, nominally compute cycle usage. Consisting of sensor reading and an user interface over HTTP, the author used the DWT unit of the ARM Cortex series to measure the compute cycles used by the sensor reading and network operations. The experiments found that the sensor readings took much more processing time than the network communication, attributed to the low-level nature of the operation.

Palavras-Chave: **Embedded Systems, IoT, Hardware.**

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things (IoT) can be defined as “[...] describes the pervasive presence of a variety of devices — such as sensors, actuators, and mobile phones — which, through unique addressing schemes, are able to interact and cooperate with each other to reach common goals” [1]. The very nature of that type of application: self-contained, with a wide range of human interactions and great telemetry needs, aligns itself greatly with the study of embedded systems.

In order to optimize and develop novel IoT products, it seems necessary to construct and understand them through the lenses of embedded systems design [2]. We can use that framework to analyze and improve IoT applications, identifying the main bottlenecks and resource drains, and applying improvements to both code logical flow and overall software architect.

The following paper describes the development of an embedded system typical of an IoT application, consisting of an sensor and network communication. Following that, an review of the overall code structure and resource consumption (CPU usage in compute cycles) is made. Finally, it discusses the improvement opportunities, and the limitations with the work and its methodology.

II. METHODOLOGY

The hardware platform which the application was built was the IMRXT1050-EVKB, an evaluation board developed by NXP using the RX1050 microcontroller unit (MCU). The development kit can be seen bellow, in Figure 1. The board was chosen due to several reasons:

1) Faculty availability: thanks to the support of NXP, the department has access to several of its hardware and development kits;

2) Market relevancy: the RX1050 is built on the ARM Cortex-M7, an series in-line with several industrial and consumer oriented markets;

3) IoT Readiness: integrated within the board, there is an FXOS8700CQ magnetometer and an ready to use ethernet jack, fulfilling the sensor and networking requirements of an typical IoT application.

Before starting development on the application, some time was taken to get used to the functionalities of the board, the peculiarities of the programming environment (IDE), MCUXpresso (also developed by NXP) and exploring the possibilities provided by the Source Development Kit (SDK) provided by the IDE. After that, work started on the application proper.

Fig. 1. The IMRXT1050-EVKB, as seen from above. Picture taken by the author.

For that matter, a simple application was developed. The microcontroller would poll the the magnetometer through its I2C bus, and convert the byte data to the corresponding pitch, roll and yaw (axial rotation) values. Alongside that, it would both send an webpage with an GUI, loaded in its memory and answer requests to from an HTTP API to send its data over the network in JSON format, so that the webpage could be updated. To achieve an fluid resolution, the webpage was configured to request new data every 100 ms. This application flow can be seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Data flow for the developed application.

For the interaction with the magnetometer, the Low Power I2C (LPI2C) driver included with the SDK was used, alongside some data formatting and presentation functions. The networking side of the application relies on the Lightweight IP (LWIP) stack, also included with the SDK. The data link and TCP/IP side of the library was left unchanged, while the HTTP library had to be changed to support API requests, as can be seen in Appendix A.

The webpage responds in real time to any changes to the axial orientation of the board, that can be detected by the magnetometer, and the gauges would change accordingly¹. The GUI available at the webpage can be seen in Figure 3.

With an clear application goal established, the profiling methodology was established. The compute cycles for the two main data flows: data from the magnetometer to the MCU and the API data from the MCU to the webpage. To achieve that, the Cortex-M7 Data Watchpoint and Trace Unit (DWT) was used. Among other parameters [3], the DWT can read the

¹The gauges don't have number indications due to the fact that the direction of positive rotation values is arbitrary, and can be chosen accordingly. The fact that the gauges change in a consistent manner was a bigger consideration in this application.

Cycle Counts (CYCCNT) at any given time. Before any one of the 2 operations, the CYCCNT was taken, and compared to the value afterwards. The result was printed to serial monitor, and the values were taken. The results found are discussed in the following section.

Fig. 3. GUI showing indicators for the 3 principal axis of rotation. From left to right: Yaw, Pitch an Roll.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment was repeated a total of 8 times, with different conditions of network connectivity and magnetometer activation. Each experiment's result can be seen in Tables I, II, III below, alongside the aggregated results for the whole experiment. All results are in compute cycles units.

TABLE I
RESULTS FOR EXPERIMENTS 1 TO 3.

	1		2		3	
	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS
Num. of Samples	493	13	369	136	42	463
Avg. Value	43129.25	197776.69	43182.19	205273.51	41023.62	190272.54
Std. Deviation	4040.91	1218.38	3927.19	162903.39	4742.07	1706.44
Max. Value	52048	199619	50828	2097942	52548	198737
Min. Value	33656	194620	33656	189692	34902	189073

As it can be seen by the results, the magnetometer read operation (indicated by the "FXOS") took much more time than the HTTP response operation (described by the "HTTP" header). One possibility is that the read operation consists of both data retrieval from the sensor IC, conversion of the byte data and formatting it to a human readable structure. Meanwhile, the network operation consisted only in the GET reply with the already formatted data.

Nevertheless, it can be said that the network operation was an order of magnitude more efficient then the sensor reading one, and that optimizations should be focused on the latter.

TABLE II
RESULTS FOR EXPERIMENTS 4 TO 6.

	4		5		6	
	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS
Num. of Samples	45	461	45	461	45	460
Avg. Value	40943.91	190329.33	40653.49	190369.26	39758.80	190350.38
Std. Deviation	4681.26	1805.63	5240.13	1826.62	4479.71	1723.53
Max. Value	51244	199299	52156	199462	49634	198633
Min. Value	34344	189022	33400	189108	32791	189075

It must be noted that the maximum value of the FXOS column represents an major anomaly, as the sample was taken

before the initialization of both the sensor and the I2C bus. In a more thorough analysis an data anomaly such as data should be removed, but it was left as to establish an upper bound for the worst case scenario. Typical values stayed around 189k and 200k compute cycles. No such anomaly could be measured for the HTTP case.

TABLE III
RESULTS FOR EXPERIMENTS 7, 8 AND AGGREGATED DATA.

	7		8		Aggr.	
	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS	HTTP	FXOS
Num. of Samples	45	461	45	460	1129	2915
Avg. Value	40752.67	190277.57	41240.84	190342.02	42578.10	191054.20
Std. Deviation	5636.74	1764.57	4720.77	1802.31	4364.28	35372.91
Max. Value	51520	199232	50364	199140	52548	2097942
Min. Value	32288	189046	33388	189073	32288	189022

One theory that can be made is that the results extend for most comparisons between memory intensive operations, and computationally intensive ones. One possibility for increasing the velocity in which the read operations are performed would be to include the sensor in a memory region closer to the processor. That could be achieved by designing an MCU packaging that already contained the relevant sensor. Another suggestion would be using faster types of physical RAM memory as MCU caches, as suggested by Chien et. al. (2016) [4]. A complete overview of this topic, nevertheless, is out of the scope of this paper.

All the files related to the application development, including source files, experimental results and supporting scripts can be found at the following Git repository.

IV. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER WORK

The main limitation of the study was time. Not only it was insufficient for developing an more comprehensive testing methodology and executing more varied tests, it had to be used to learn and configure the development environment and the processor platform.

An continuation of this work should focus on developing a more complete IoT application, with an clear sensing goal, and a more robust and configurable user interface. Furthermore, it would bennefit from having different types of sensors using different communication standards (I2C, 4-20 mA current Loop, RS232 i.e.), alongside more widely used communication protocols (HTTP for interface and MQTT for telemetry, for instance). Another approach would be using a a more IoT focused MCU, as the IMRXT1050 platform by the nature of its design is focused on industrial applications [5]. More low-power and lower-performance units could be used, such as the STM32 or ESP86/32 series. Other software architectures could be used, such as an interrupt-based or state machine approach, in contrast to the infinite loop polling that was used.

The profiling of energy characteristics, mainly power consumption, could be also an interesting idea for an upcoming paper. Not only is that an increasing necessity due to the growing number of IoT devices and networks [6], profiling

the power profile of the different parts of an sensor-network system could lead to more focused optimizations and guide more efficient design practices.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Considering the time constraints and the challenges of programming in an new platform, the results obtained were satisfactory. Not only this work illustrates, at least, some of the challenges encountered on the development and design of an IoT application, but it was able the replicate the functionalities of an typical market product. Despite needing more work before any decisive conclusion, the results found are coherent and do reflect the typical behavior of an sesoring system, with network functionalities.

It is hoped that this paper will serve as starting point for future studies on the topic of IoT optimization and embedded systems profiling, and that its results can help guide designers and engineers into developing more efficient products and solutions.

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APPENDIX A

MODDIFIED LWIP HTTP IMPLEMENTATION

```

1 static err_t
2 http_find_file(struct http_state *hs, const char *
   uri, int is_09)
3 {
4     size_t loop;
5     struct fs_file *file = NULL;
6     char *params = NULL;
7     err_t err;
8     #if LWIP_HTTPD_CGI
9         int i;
10        #endif /* LWIP_HTTPD_CGI */
11        #if !LWIP_HTTPD_SSI
12            const
13        #endif /* !LWIP_HTTPD_SSI */
14        /* By default, assume we will not be processing
15         server-side-includes tags */
16        u8_t tag_check = 0;
17
18        /* Have we been asked for the default file (in
19         root or a directory) ? */
20        #if LWIP_HTTPD_MAX_REQUEST_URI_LEN
21            size_t uri_len = strlen(uri);
22

```

```

23
24 // if the uri starts with "/api", defer handling
25 // to http_handle_api_call
26 if(strncmp(uri, "/api", 4) == 0){
27     return http_handle_api_call(hs, uri, is_09);
28 }
29 ...
30 } //end http_find_file
31 static err_t
32 http_handle_api_call(struct http_state *hs, const
33 char *uri, int is_09){
34     char api = 0;
35     if(strcmp(uri, "/api/button/") == 0){
36         //PRINTF("Button api called.\r\n");
37         api = 0;
38     }
39     if(strcmp(uri, "/api/ecompass/") == 0){
40         //PRINTF("Ecompass api called.\r\n");
41         api = 1;
42     }
43
44     size_t buf_len = 0;
45     char *buffer = get_byte_buffer(&buf_len, api);
46     if (buffer != NULL) {
47         hs->original_file = buffer;
48         hs->file = hs->original_file;
49         //PRINTF("Original file: %p\r\n", hs->file);
50         hs->handle = (struct fs_file*) NULL;
51         hs->left = buf_len;
52         hs->is_dynamic = true;
53         return ERR_OK;
54     }else{
55         return ERR_MEM;
56     }
57 }
58 static void
59 http_state_free(struct http_state *hs)
60 {
61     if (hs != NULL) {
62         http_state_eof(hs);
63         http_remove_connection(hs);
64
65         // if memory was allocated to send a custom
66         // html/json buffer, free it
67         if(hs->original_file != NULL && hs->is_dynamic)
68         {
69             //PRINTF("File: %p\r\n", hs->original_file)
70             ;
71             mem_free(hs->original_file);
72         }
73     }
74     HTTP_FREE_HTTP_STATE(hs);
75 }

```

The specifics of the API handling can be seen on the rest api C file, on the application repository.